

Arrange Your Magnets to Tailor Homogeneous Fields

Peter Blümler
Ingo Kefenberg
Bayreuth
&
Mainz

A Tax-Free Toy: The Graphical User Interface

Single-Sided Focusing Yields Elevated Saddle Points

Curvature Collapse via Twisted Sandwiches

Continuum Theory That Delivers

More Magnets Provide Better Fields?

Icosahedral symmetry is not just cool anymore

A Tax-Free Toy: The **G**raphical **U**ser **I**nterface

Animation of dipole configurations discussed in: Ingo Rehberg and Peter Blümler, Analytic approach to creating homogeneous fields with finite-size magnets. Phys. Rev. Applied 23, 064029 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.1103/9nnk-jytn>

(x, y) = (9.7, 12.8)

configurations:

- $H_r\alpha$
- H_a
- $f\alpha$
- $f_2\alpha$
- $H_2\alpha$
- $h\alpha$
- $h_2\alpha$
- myCl

3d view options:

- r_e
- r_a
- r_r
- $ostp$
- 3D
- xy
- xz
- yz

add-on:

- flat
- \vec{m}
- axs
- shell

field comp:

- B_x
- B_y
- B_z

size 0.010
 R 0.035

- Icosahedron
- Icosahedron 90
- Sandwich, optimal

Fig s:

-
-
-
-
-

Links:

-
-
-
-

pop-ups:

- Ti
- Fo
- QR

Control Panel:

- size
- R
- Icosahedron
- Icosahedron 90
- Sandwich, optimal

Halbach Rings Fail in Real Space

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twist

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Dipole orientations to maximize B_z

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Name	Faces	Vertices	Edges	Symmetry	Order
Tetrahedron	4	4	6	T _d	1
Cube (Hexahedron)	6	8	12	O _h	2
Octahedron	8	6	12	O _h	2
Dodecahedron	12	20	30	I _h	4
Icosahedron	20	12	30	I _h	4
Truncated tetrahedron	8	12	18	T _d	1
Cuboctahedron	14	12	24	O _h	2
Truncated cube	14	24	36	O _h	2
Truncated octahedron	14	24	36	O _h	2
Rhombicuboctahedron	26	24	48	O _h	2
Truncated cuboctahedron	26	48	72	O _h	2
Snub cube	38	24	60	O (chiral)	2
Icosidodecahedron	32	30	60	I _h	4
Truncated dodecahedron	32	60	90	I _h	4
Truncated icosahedron	32	60	90	I _h	4
Rhombicosidodecahedron	62	60	120	I _h	4
Truncated icosidodecahedron	62	120	180	I _h	4
Snub dodecahedron	92	60	150	I (chiral)	4

Tailoring Magnet Setups for Field Homogeneity: An Interactive GUI for Design and Exploration

I. Rehberg¹, P. Blümler²

¹Institute of Physics, University of Bayreuth

²Institute of Physics, Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz

Introduction

Special arrangements of permanent magnets along a ring yield an almost homogeneous field useful for applications [1]. A dipole orientation $\alpha = 2\varphi$, as originally introduced for extended magnetic rods [2], yields a reasonable amount of homogeneity even for such finite-size magnets as shown in Fig. 1. A slight modification of this arrangement in the plane, namely

$$\tan \alpha = \frac{3 \sin(2\varphi)}{6 \cos^2 \varphi - 2}, \quad (1)$$

optimizes the field strength [3] and increases its homogeneity [4]. Adapting this approach to the third dimension leads to so-called focussed configurations [4].

Figure 1. Sixteen neodymium 1 cm^3 cubes form a prototype used for the focussed configuration measurements in [4].

Methods

An open-source Python script supports interactive exploration of the findings of Ref. [4]. It provides a graphical user interface (GUI) available for download to aid the design of novel experimental arrangements [5]. This presentation indicates some of the capabilities of that GUI.

Results for Rings and Sandwiches

In the following, screenshots from [5] highlight five key results of [4].

- **Halbach Rings:** If built of N infinitely long rods the centre field forms a saddle point of order N shown in Fig. 2.

$$B_x(\rho) - B_x(0) \propto \rho^{16}$$

Figure 2. Calculated field for a ring of 16 infinitely long rods. The extreme flatness means that a change is only visible at the largest distance from the centre, the 4 corners.

- **Finite-size magnets:** For cuboids, disks, spheres, and other finite-size shapes, the field changes generically with the second power, e.g. Fig. 3.

Figure 3. The change of the fields with the distance from the centre.

- **Tilt:** Allowing for a tilt (Fig. 4) of the magnets with respect to their ring planes focusses the field to finite distances from that ring, a feature useful for single-sided NMR and other applications.

Figure 4. Side view of tilted cuboids located along a ring.

- **Singular arrangements:** At singular heights of a stacked (sandwich, see Fig. 5) ring configuration, the centre field might achieve a quartic (flat) maximum.

Figure 5. A sandwich construction of two planar rings.

- **Twist:** To achieve the circular homogeneity desirable for imaging applications, a twisted sandwich is helpful (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. The strength of B_x forms a quartic maximum here due to a suitable twist in a stack of two rings.

Annular and Spherical Arrangements: Outlook

Another interactive tool for designing magnet distributions to achieve homogeneous fields experimentally will be available in the updated version of the GUI [5]. Based on the theory for continuous distributions of magnetization for both annular disks and spherical shells it allows estimating the field on a percentage level with a compact analytic formula and an interactive modification of the inner and outer diameter of the annular disk. Figure 7 illustrates, e.g., that one cannot afford an inner radius R_{in} which is larger than the height of the magnets h , to obtain field strengths of 50 % of the remanence B_r of the magnets.

Figure 7. The field stemming from a continuous distribution of magnetization on an infinite annular disk following either the Halbach (grey dashed) or the focussed orientation (red solid line). Screenshot from an update of [5].

In contrast to this restriction, spherical distributions produce fields that diverge logarithmically with the outer radius R_{out} of the spherical shell. A practical approach to optimized spherical distributions of magnetization is to arrange magnets at the vertices of Platonic solids. *Focussing* onto the origin yields the configuration with the largest field [4]. Version 2.1.1 of the *Dipole Cluster Inspector* visualizes the orientations and fields for all Platonic and Archimedean solids [6].

Figure 8. A stereoscopic image of the magnetic dipoles arranged at the vertices of a dodecahedron and set in the focussing orientation. Screenshot from an update of [6].

References

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